

Student Engagement and Public Schools Blended Learning Environment in Governor Generoso South District

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Abstract.

The study unfolded the extent of the blended learning environment about student engagement during post-pandemic in public schools. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of online content was pervasive; synchronous and asynchronous learning and learning management systems were vast, and assessment methods were extensive, while the extent of student engagement in terms of initiative in research or project and completion of the assignment was extensive. Inquiry, curiosity, and quality of work are moderately extensive. There was a significant relationship between a blended learning environment and student engagement. All domains of a blended learning environment significantly influence student engagement in terms of online content, learning management systems, synchronous and asynchronous, and assessment methods suggest significant influences in student engagement. Future research may undertake comparative analyses of different blended learning models and implementations to identify best practices. Explore how variations in technology use, teacher training, and student demographics may influence outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. student engagement
2. blended learning environment
3. synchronous and asynchronous learning
4. learning management system

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1. Introduction

The study is rooted in the need to address the evolving educational demands and challenges of integrating technology in public school settings. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, schools worldwide have adopted blended learning environments, combining traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning. This shift has underscored the importance of understanding how such environments impact student engagement, a critical factor influencing academic success and overall student development. Governor Generoso South District, representative of many rural areas, faces unique challenges in implementing blended learning due to varying levels of access to technology, infrastructure, and teacher preparedness. By ex-

amining student engagement within this context, the study aims to provide insights into practical strategies for enhancing learning outcomes and inform policy and practice to support the equitable and effective integration of blended learning in similar districts. The global response to the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of blended learning models, combining in-person and online instruction, to ensure continued access to education while safeguarding public health. However, the implementation and effectiveness of these models have varied widely across countries. International scenarios have witnessed diverse approaches to technology integration, resource availability, and educational policies directly influencing student engagement. In some regions, access to technology and digital resources remains challenging, creating disparities in student engagement and learning outcomes (Poort et al., 2023). The post-pandemic era has seen the widespread adoption of blended learning, offering students flexibility and adaptability in their educational journeys. However, it has also brought forth many challenges that students must navigate. Among the foremost challenges is the digital divide, with disparities in access to technology and reliable internet connections. Many students need more devices and internet access, hindering their full participation in the online components of blended learning. Additionally, the shift to virtual learning has increased screen time and raised concerns about digital fatigue and mental health (Seregar et al., 2023). Students are often required to adapt to new digital tools and platforms, which can be overwhelming and impact their engagement. Maintaining self-discipline and motivation without the structure of traditional classrooms is another challenge. Time management and the absence of in-person teacher support for immediate clarification also present obstacles. Moreover, students miss valuable social interactions and extracurricular activities, affecting their well-being. In

a post-pandemic world, addressing these challenges is critical to ensure that blended learning remains an effective and equitable educational approach for all students (Yang et al., 2023). Student engagement in blended learning within the Philippine education system presents a unique dynamic. After the pandemic, the Philippine educational landscape rapidly shifted to incorporate online and blended learning models. Students have engaged in this transition by leveraging digital platforms and technologies to access educational materials, attend virtual classes, and collaborate with peers and teachers. However, they have encountered distinct challenges (Peters et al., 2022). The digital divide remains a significant issue, with students in more remote or economically disadvantaged areas needing more devices and stable internet connections. This inequality has made access to blended learning resources unequal. Additionally, the Philippines' diverse geography and socioeconomic conditions need to be revised to standardize the quality and delivery of blended education. Students often need to adapt to different modes of learning, including asynchronous and synchronous methods, which can impact their engagement levels. Time management and maintaining motivation in a more self-directed learning environment have also been hurdles. Furthermore, the absence of in-person interactions has affected social development and extracurricular participation. In the Philippine context, addressing these challenges is imperative to ensure that blended learning is an inclusive and effective mode of education for all students (Piña, 2022). Teachers in Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental, have emphasized clear and consistent communication with students. This includes providing detailed instructions, schedules, and expectations for online and in-person learning activities. Teachers have leveraged various interactive online platforms to create engaging and dynamic virtual classrooms. They use video conferencing, dis-

cussion forums, and digital whiteboards to facilitate discussions, collaborative projects, and live lessons. Recognizing the diverse needs of their students, teachers offer individualized support and feedback. This includes one-on-one virtual meetings, personalized learning plans, and targeted assistance to address specific learning challenges. Teachers integrate multimedia and digital resources into their lessons, such as educational videos, interactive simulations, and gamified content, to make learning more engaging and enjoyable. These interventions reflect teachers' dedication to enhancing student engagement in the blended learning environment and ensuring that students receive a quality education during the challenges posed by the post-pandemic era.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—This section reviews significant literature on blended learning environments, online content, learning management systems, and student engagement. Blended learning combines in-person instruction with online components, offering a flexible, dynamic approach that has become essential post-pandemic. Research by Cannon et al. (2023) and Kara et al. (2023) underscores the importance of metacognition, self-efficacy, and positive attitudes in improving student performance in blended courses. Studies also highlight the growing acceptance and effectiveness of blended learning among educators, as seen in Turkey's elementary education system.

1.1.1. Online Content—Online Content is crucial in a blended learning environment, offering students flexibility and fostering self-directed learning. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of online content, with studies by Ali et al. (2023) and Han et al. (2022) showing its positive impact on grammar performance and learning outcomes in blended settings. Learning Management Systems (LMS) serve as the backbone of blended learning, facilitating content delivery and student engagement.

Research by Goh and Yang (2021) and Dankers et al. (2022) highlights the role of LMS in enhancing student success and continuous use of e-learning systems.

1.1.2. Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning—Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning are integral to blended learning, providing real-time and flexible learning options. Studies by Piña (2022) and Zhang et al. (2023) compare these modes' effectiveness, emphasizing the importance of teaching presence and social engagement in both contexts.

1.1.3. Assessment Methods—Assessment Methods are essential in evaluating student progress in blended learning. Research by Çiftçi (2020) and Uygur (2022) indicates that blended learning methods significantly enhance academic achievement and knowledge retention compared to traditional face-to-face learning.

1.1.4. Student Engagement—Student Engagement is a key indicator of academic success in blended learning environments. Studies by Yang et al. (2023) and Siregar et al. (2023) explore the factors influencing student engagement, including feedback, lecturer leadership, and course relevance. Quality of work and assignment completion are also critical indicators of engagement, as shown by research from Peters et al. (2022) and Soffer and Cohen (2019).

1.1.5. Inquiry and Curiosity—Inquiry and Curiosity drive student engagement, fostering a deeper understanding and critical thinking. Wu and Wu (2020) and Wu et al. (2018) highlight the role of curiosity and engagement in developing inquiry abilities, emphasizing the importance of both formal and informal learning experiences.

1.1.6. Initiative in Research or Projects—Initiative in Research or Projects is a strong indicator of student engagement, reflecting a proactive approach to learning. Yuksel et al. (2021) and Borish et al. (2022) discuss the effectiveness of client-sponsored projects and student-designed lab projects in enhancing stu-

dent engagement and modeling skills.

1.2. Theoretical Framework—Self-determination theory (SDT) was a comprehensive psychological framework that explores the motivation behind human behavior and how individuals find meaning and satisfaction in their actions. Developed by Deci and Ryan in the 1980s, SDT posits that people have innate psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. These needs are the foundation of motivation and are central to understanding why individuals engage in specific activities or tasks (Borish et al., 2022). In SDT, autonomy refers to the desire for self-directed actions and choices. People are most motivated when they feel their behavior aligns with their values and interests. Competence is the need to feel adequate and capable of performing tasks. When individuals experience a sense of mastery and growth, they are more likely to engage in activities willingly. Finally, relatedness pertains to the need for social connection and a sense of belonging. Humans are inherently social beings, and they thrive when they feel connected to others and supported by their communities (Yuksel et al., 2021). The theory suggests that satisfying these psychological needs promotes intrinsic motivation, the most potent form. Intrinsic motivation arises from a genuine interest in the activity rather than external rewards or pressures. SDT also recognizes extrinsic motivation, ranging from control, like doing something for rewards or to avoid punishment, to autonomous, like doing something because it aligns with personal values. Researchers and practitioners often use SDT to understand and enhance motivation in various contexts, including education, work, sports, and health, by designing environments that support individuals' autonomy, competence, and relatedness needs. In education, SDT has played a significant role in promoting student engagement, as it highlights the importance of creating learning environments where students have a say in their education, can build

competence, and feel connected to their peers and teachers. Figure 1 shows the interaction of the indicators given the variables under study. In the study examining student engagement in post-pandemic blended learning environments, Self-Determination Theory (SDT) can be applied to understand the underlying motivations and factors influencing students' engagement and participation. The theory's argument and contentions offer a valuable lens through which researchers can analyze the dynamics of student engagement in this context. SDT posits that individuals are most motivated and engaged when their psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are satisfied. These principles can guide the study's framework and analysis in blended learning. The theory's contention that autonomy is essential for motivation suggests that allowing students control over their learning experiences and choices can foster greater engagement. Researchers may investigate the impact of students' ability to make choices about the pace, sequence, or mode of their learning and how this autonomy influences their engagement. Secondly, the theory's emphasis on competence underscores the significance of providing students with opportunities to experience success, mastery, and growth in their learning. The study can explore how various aspects of blended learning, such as adaptive digital resources or differentiated instruction, contribute to students' sense of competence and, subsequently, their level of engagement. Thirdly, relatedness contends that fostering social connections and community can enhance motivation. Researchers can investigate the role of teacher-student relationships, peer interactions, and collaborative activities in the blended learning environment, as these elements can significantly impact students' feelings of connectedness and engagement. In summary, applying SDT in the study allows an in-depth exploration of how autonomy, competence, and relatedness needs impact student

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study engagement in post-pandemic blended learning environments.

By understanding the underlying motivations and factors through the lens of SDT, researchers can inform educational practices and strategies that better support and enhance student engagement in these dynamic and evolving learning contexts.

1.3. Statement of the Problem—The study was purposely conducted to evaluate student engagement in post-pandemic public schools’ blended learning environment in Governor Generoso South, Davao Oriental. This specifically sought to answer the following statement of the problem:

- (1) What is the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of;
 - (1) online content;
 - (2) learning management system;
 - (3) synchronous and asynchronous learning; and
 - (4) assessment methods?
- (2) What is the extent of student engagement in terms of;
 - (1) completion of assignment;
 - (2) quality of work;
 - (3) inquiry and curiosity; and
 - (4) initiative in research or project?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between a blended learning environment and student engagement?
- (4) Which of the domains of blended learning environments significantly influences student engagement?

1.4. Hypotheses—To provide empirical evidence given the posed theoretical and conceptual frameworks as claimed by the study, null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance, stating: Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between a blended learning en-

vironment and student engagement; and, Ho 2: None from among the domains of blended learning environment significantly influence student engagement. The study quantitatively assessed the correlation between MTB-MLE implementation and kindergarten infrastructure in Banay-

banay District, Davao Oriental. Results will be of significance to the following: School Principal and Administrators. The study gives administrators valuable insights into the factors influencing student engagement in blended learning. This information allows them to make data-informed decisions regarding technology integration, curriculum design, and resource allocation. Findings can help administrators refine and enhance their blended learning programs, optimizing the educational experience for students and teachers. Understanding the drivers of student engagement can help administrators allocate resources effectively, ensuring that teachers and students have the necessary tools and support to thrive in blended learning environments. Administrators can use the study's findings to provide teachers with targeted support and professional development opportunities to enhance their effectiveness in blended learning settings. Teachers. Teachers can gain a deeper understanding of the factors that influence student engagement, allowing them to tailor their teaching methods and strategies to better meet their students' needs. Insights from the study can inform teachers on how to provide personalized support and resources to students, addressing individual engagement challenges. Teachers can use the study's findings to continuously improve their teaching practices in blended learning environments, enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. Parents and community Parents can benefit from the study's findings to better support their children's education. They can gain insights into the challenges and opportunities of blended learning and provide more effective assistance at home. Parents can use the study's insights to collaborate with teachers and administrators to create a supportive home learning environment that complements the blended learning experience. Future Researchers. The study serves as a foundation for future research, enabling scholars to delve deeper into specific aspects of student engagement in blended learning environments. Future researchers can use the study's findings to compare engagement trends over time or across different settings, helping to identify evolving patterns and best practices. In summary, a study on student engagement in post-pandemic blended learning environments provides actionable insights and benefits to many stakeholders, from school administrators and teachers who aim to improve educational practices to parents who seek to support their children's learning. Additionally, it paves the way for further research, fostering the growth of knowledge in this critical area of education. The following are variables in the study that are conceptually and operationally defined; A blended learning environment in public schools is an instructional approach that combines traditional, face-to-face classroom instruction with online or digital learning components. This learning model seeks to leverage the advantages of in-person and online learning to create a more flexible, personalized, and practical educational experience for students. The key characteristics of a blended learning environment in public schools include integrating technology into the curriculum, personalized learning pathways that cater to individual student needs, and the flexibility to adapt to different learning styles and paces. It aims to provide students with a well-rounded education that combines the benefits of in-person interactions with the convenience and opportunities offered by digital tools and resources. Blended learning environments in public schools have become particularly relevant in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, as they allow for more adaptive and resilient educational approaches that can accommodate a variety of circumstances and learning modalities. Student engagement refers to the active involvement, participation, and investment of students in their learning experiences, both within and beyond the classroom. This multifaceted concept transcends traditional definitions, reflect-

ing the evolving dynamics of education in the wake of the pandemic. Post-pandemic student engagement encompasses a student's dedication to academic tasks, emotional connection to the learning process, ability to adapt to various learning modalities, and resilience in the face of disruption.

2. Methodology

Research methods encompass a variety of approaches, including quantitative methods, which involve collecting numerical data through means such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis. Conversely, qualitative methods focus on comprehending and interpreting non-numerical data, utilizing interviews, content analysis, or ethnography. Research methods are systematic procedures employed to gather and analyze data to address research inquiries and achieve specific objectives. These methods form the cornerstone of empirical investigations across various disciplines, encompassing the natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work during its preparation meticulously. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—Within the realm of research, non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs stand as significant methodologies, each possessing unique intentions and attributes. Non-experimental research chiefly centers on observing and analyzing preexisting phenomena without intervening in manipulating variables. Descriptive research exhaustively and meticulously portrays a specific scenario, population, or occurrence. (Creswell, 2014). Correlational research, on the other hand, examines the relationships between variables, aiming to identify patterns, associations, or connections among them. It does not imply causation but helps researchers understand how changes in one variable may relate to changes in another. Predictive research design extends beyond describing and correlating variables. It involves developing models or theories to predict future outcomes or behavior. Researchers gather and analyze data to establish patterns that can be used for forecasting or making informed decisions. While these research designs serve distinct purposes, they share common advantages. They offer practicality, allowing researchers to study phenomena as they naturally occur, which is often the case in the social sciences. Non-experimental research designs are more ethical and logistically feasible when manipulation or experimentation is inappropriate or impossible. However, a limitation is the need for more control over variables, making it challenging to establish causal relationships. Researchers may employ non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs to evaluate student engagement in post-pandemic public schools' blended learning environments to gain valuable insights into the complex relationships and factors influencing student engagement. These research designs play a significant role in comprehensively understanding the dynamics of student engagement in the context of blended learning. Non-experimental research designs, such as descriptive and correlational approaches, are particularly relevant as they focus on observation and analysis rather than manipulating variables. Descriptive research helps researchers

in this study provide a detailed, holistic snapshot of student engagement in blended learning settings by documenting various aspects, such as attendance, participation, and assignment completion. This information lays the foundation for a comprehensive understanding of the current state of engagement in post-pandemic blended learning environments. Conversely, correlation research is instrumental in identifying potential relationships and patterns between various variables. Predictive research design takes the study further by attempting to forecast or predict future outcomes based on the collected data. In this context, predictive research can help educators and policymakers anticipate and address potential challenges in student engagement. By employing non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs, this study provides a snapshot of the current state of student engagement. It offers insights into the potential causes and future trends. These designs are essential for educators and policymakers to create more effective and engaging blended learning environments in post-pandemic public schools.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the Secondary School Teachers in Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, and 100 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from the private schools surrounding the district. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified through online platforms and in person, considering the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its significance to their professional development. The selection of participants was guided by the presumption that they were actively involved in the management and supervision of schools, particularly in organizational oversight and instructional supervision. It was anticipated that these individuals possessed a solid commitment to curriculum im-

plementation policies, pedagogical classroom practices, and the day-to-day administration of diverse school-based initiatives, projects, and activities aimed at promoting the holistic development of early learners within the framework of public school management. The criteria for inclusion in this study were based on the expectation that they had made significant contributions that extended beyond their core responsibilities related to curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, as evidenced by their active participation in various educational endeavors. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all to improve the school environment and learners' educational experiences during the new regular learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system.

2.3. Research Instrument—In this research study, the instrument utilized was thoughtfully designed through an exhaustive examination of existing literature and pertinent studies. The researcher invested significant time and effort in collecting and analyzing relevant literature, extracting essential concepts that informed the construction of the instrument and reinforced its alignment with the specified research themes. This meticulous process resulted in developing a well-organized set of questionnaire items, thereby enhancing the overall validity of the instrument and minimizing potential threats to its reliability. As the authors argued, items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of a blended learning environment in terms of online content, learning management systems, synchronous and asynchronous learning, and assessment methods. Likewise, the second part of the survey eval-

uated student engagement regarding assignment completion, quality of work, inquiry, curiosity, and initiative in research or projects. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.886, meaning

there is an 88.6 percent confidence level in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of the blended learning environment. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The blended learning environment is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The blended learning environment is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The blended learning environment is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The blended learning environment is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The blended learning environment is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of student engagement, a 5-point Likert scale was

used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The student engagement is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The student engagement is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The student engagement is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The student engagement is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The student engagement is not manifested

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The statements provide a clear overview of the sequential steps that define the data collection process. It was imperative that the researcher carefully consider and strictly follow these steps, adhering to the policies of Rizal Memorial Colleges and the guidelines set forth by the IATF. This approach was vital to ensure safety and

mitigate any potential risks associated with gathering relevant data, especially given the current context of ongoing in-person interactions. Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of December 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently, she prepared various documents, including re-

quest letters, for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2004) outlined, and followed the health protocols mandated by the IATF's policy. As the research proposal was approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of February to the first week of March 2024, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within Governor Generoso, South District to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the first week of May 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime in the second week of May 2024 and further deepen the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results in the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were a cornerstone in upholding the integrity and safeguarding the rights of individuals within research and educational pursuits. In voluntary participation, ethics reinforce the

principle that individuals should make a deliberate, uncoerced choice to engage in any activity or study. Central to this ethical framework is informed consent, which entails furnishing participants with thorough details regarding the nature, objectives, potential risks, and benefits of the activity or research. Voluntary Participation. The researcher's duty in conveying information about voluntary participation involved providing clear and comprehensive insights into the study and the respondent's role within it. She had to guarantee that participants fully grasped the research's purpose, goals, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits associated with their involvement. Furthermore, she clarified the data collection, storage, and utilization methods with an unwavering commitment to maintaining confidentiality and preserving privacy. Securing informed consent, typically facilitated through written consent forms, was an essential ethical prerequisite. It ensured that participants made well-informed, self-directed decisions regarding their participation, showcasing the utmost respect for their autonomy and rights throughout the research endeavor.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of the blended learning environment and statement problem number two (2) regarding the extent of student engagement. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between blended learning environment and student engagement. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4 on the indicators of a blended learning environment that significantly influences student engagement (Pallant, 2000), (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations

followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter focuses on presenting, analyzing, and interpreting the collected data. Both tabular and textual formats enhance the depth of analysis and draw meaningful implications. This serves as further evidence supporting the hypothesis's claim.

3.1. The extent of Blended Learning Environment— A blended learning environment is a dynamic and flexible educational approach that combines traditional, in-person instruction with online and digital learning components. It represents a fusion of face-to-face classroom teaching with technology-driven learning opportunities. In this model, students engage in a mix of on-site classroom sessions and online activities, allowing them to access educational content, collaborate with peers, and interact with teachers through digital platforms. Blended learning aims to harness the advantages of both traditional and online learning, offering students a well-rounded educational experience that combines the benefits of personal interaction, active engagement, and the convenience and flexibility of digital resources. It recognizes that students have diverse learning styles and needs and adapts to meet them by offering various resources and instructional methods. Blended learning environments have gained prominence in the post-pandemic era, as they provide a resilient and adaptable approach to education, capable of responding to various circumstances and educational modalities.

*3.1.1. Online Content—*Online content was a pivotal indicator of a blended learning environment, reflecting the integration of digital resources into the educational landscape. In this context, online content encompasses various digital materials, including text, video, interactive modules, and multimedia resources, designed to support and enhance the learning experience. These digital resources are carefully curated and aligned with the curriculum, providing students with accessible and on-demand access to educational materials. Online content offers students flexibility in engaging with the course material and fosters self-directed learning, allowing them to explore topics at their own pace. Moreover, the diversity and quality of online content indicate the degree of investment in the blended learning environment. It underscores the importance of catering to varied learning styles and preferences. It creates an immersive, interactive, and engaging atmosphere central to blended learning initiatives' success in both traditional and post-pandemic educational settings. Table 1 shows the extent of the blended learning environment regarding online content. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: An indicator of a well-designed blended learning environment is the provision of personalized online content that allows students to tailor their learning experience. This includes adaptive learning platforms and customizable resources (4.50); in a dynamic blended learning setting, the ability to update and revise online content in real-time serves as an indicator of responsiveness to evolving educational needs and the integration of current information (4.40) and The presence of online content that aligns closely with learning objectives and curriculum goals indicates that the materials have been thoughtfully curated to support the educational outcomes of the blended learning program (4.20) are always manifested. Engaging online content that encourages active participation, such as gamified modules, discussion forums, and multimedia simulations,

is a crucial indicator of an interactive and immersive blended learning environment that promotes student engagement and more profound understanding (4.12) and the presence of diverse and easily accessible online content, including multimedia resources, interactive modules, and digital textbooks, is a crucial indicator of a rich blended learning environment. This diversity caters to various learning styles and preferences (4.00), often manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.24 denotes the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of online content that is continually manifested and, thus, very extensive. The results were reflected by Ali et al. (2023), who aimed to investigate the impact of both online and blended learning methods on grammatical knowledge and skill acquisition via an experimental approach. Although both approaches significantly improved learners' gram-

mar performance, the study results discovered significantly higher performance in a blended learning environment than solely online learning. On the other hand, Han et al. (2022) use digital traces to help identify students' online learning strategies by making a clear distinction between the descriptive features (the proportional distribution of students' different online learning actions) and quantitative aspects (the total number of the online learning sessions). This distinction has not been adequately addressed in extant research. It also examines the extent to which the descriptive features and quantitative aspects of students' observed online learning behaviors are related to students' self-reported perceptions of the blended learning environment and the academic learning outcomes.

Table 1. The Extent of Blended Learning Environment in Terms of Online Content

No	Online Content	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The presence of diverse and easily accessible online content, including multimedia resources, interactive modules, and digital textbooks, is a key indicator of a rich blended learning environment. This diversity caters to various learning styles and preferences.	4.00	Extensive
2	An indicator of a well-designed blended learning environment is the provision of personalized online content that allows students to tailor their learning experiences. This includes adaptive learning platforms and customizable resources.	4.50	Very Extensive
3	In a dynamic blended learning setting, the ability to update and revise online content in real-time serves as an indicator of responsiveness to evolving educational needs and the integration of current information.	4.40	Very Extensive
4	The presence of online content that aligns closely with learning objectives and curriculum goals indicates that the materials have been thoughtfully curated to support the educational outcomes of the blended learning program.	4.20	Very Extensive
5	Engaging online content that encourages active participation, such as gamified modules, discussion forums, and multimedia simulations, is a crucial indicator of an interactive and immersive blended learning environment that promotes student engagement and deeper understanding.	4.12	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.24	Very Extensive

The content-oriented learners had significantly more online learning sessions and performed significantly better on formative and summative assessments than their practice-oriented counterparts. Moreover, a higher proportion of students reporting more negative perceptions were observed to adopt practice-oriented strategies. In contrast, more students reporting better perceptions were observed to adopt content-oriented strategies. The study results are triangulated evidence for the previous self-reported research on the relations between students' perceptions and strategies. The study's results also offer several ideas for teaching and curriculum design in blended courses to improve the quality of students' blended learning experiences.

3.1.2. Learning Management Systems—A Learning Management System (LMS) is a fundamental indicator of a blended learning environment, serving as the central infrastructure that supports and facilitates the seamless integration of online and in-person learning. It is a digital platform that enables educators to organize, deliver, and manage educational content and resources while providing students with a structured, user-friendly interface for accessing materials, participating in discussions, submitting assignments, and tracking their progress. An effective LMS offers many features, including course management, communication tools, assessment and grading capabilities, and data analytics. Its presence in a blended learning environment signifies the institution's commitment to optimizing the learning experience. It enables educators to deliver content efficiently, monitor student engagement and performance, and provide timely feedback. Moreover, it fosters collaboration, allowing students to interact with their peers and teachers in real-time and asynchronous. The utilization and effectiveness of an LMS are critical indicators of the adaptability and technological integration of a blended learning environment, ultimately

enhancing the overall educational experience. Table 2 shows the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of learning management systems. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: An LMS that provides communication and collaboration tools, such as discussion boards, chat features, and group project spaces, is a significant indicator of a collaborative and interactive blended learning environment (4.10), The ability to conduct assessments, quizzes, and track student progress within the LMS is an indicator of a well-integrated system that supports formative and summative assessment in the blended learning environment (3.50) and A user-friendly LMS interface, with straightforward navigation and intuitive design, is an indicator of an accessible blended learning environment that supports the diverse needs of students (3.45) are oftentimes manifested. An LMS that offers data analytics and reporting features for both educators and students is an essential indicator of a data-informed blended learning environment that can help monitor and improve student performance and engagement (3.45) and An LMS serves as a central repository for course materials, making it easy for students to access resources, assignments, and course content, which is a crucial indicator of an organized and streamlined blended learning environment (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.46 denotes the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of learning management systems, which is oftentimes manifested and, thus, extensive.

E-learning systems are widely deployed in higher education institutions, but sustaining students continued use of e-learning systems remains challenging. Goh and Yang (2021) investigated the relationship between e-learning engagement, flow experience, and learning management system continuance via a mediated moderation interaction model.

Table 2. The Extent of Blended Learning Environment in Terms of Learning Management Systems

No	Learning Management Systems	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	An LMS serves as a central repository for course materials, making it easy for students to access resources, assignments, and course content, which is a key indicator of an organized and streamlined blended learning environment.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	A user-friendly LMS interface, with clear navigation and intuitive design, is an indicator of an accessible blended learning environment that supports the diverse needs of students.	3.45	Extensive
3	An LMS that provides communication and collaboration tools, such as discussion boards, chat features, and group project spaces, is a significant indicator of a collaborative and interactive blended learning environment.	4.10	Extensive
4	The ability to conduct assessments, quizzes, and track student progress within the LMS is an indicator of a well-integrated system that supports formative and summative assessment in the blended learning environment.	3.50	Extensive
5	An LMS that offers data analytics and reporting features for both educators and students is an important indicator of a data-informed blended learning environment that can help monitor and improve student performance and engagement.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.46	Extensive

The analysis shows that flow mediates e-engagement and perceived ease of use, directly impacting e-learning system continuance. Flow has an indirect impact through perceived usefulness on e-learning system continuance. However, the direct impact of flow on system continuance weakens as e-learning engagement increases. This finding explains flow’s mixed and inconsistent impact in the e-learning system continuance literature. The dual effect of flow suggests that instructors must carefully balance pedagogical decisions intended to heighten flow experience to generate positive learning outcomes through e-engagement and its consequence of reduced impact on continued system use. Student success and the perceptions of success are growing areas of research. Dankers et al. (2022) investigated the perceptions of lecturers and students of the Art Faculty regarding student success and whether perceptions of

student success, the use of technologies, and blended teaching and learning approaches were interrelated. All participants agreed that using a learning management system to enhance a blended learning approach contributed to student success. These findings agreed with other research conducted by international scholars. More research on how technologies impact the success of individual students and the interrelatedness of technologies, learning approaches, and student success is necessary.

3.1.3. Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning—The concepts of synchronous and asynchronous learning are integral indicators of a blended learning environment, reflecting the flexibility and adaptability of educational approaches. Synchronous learning refers to real-time interactions between students and instructors, often facilitated through live virtual classes, video conferences, or chat sessions. It enables

immediate engagement and dynamic communication, resembling traditional classroom experiences, and allows students to interact, ask questions, and receive instant feedback. Table 3 shows the extent of the blended learning environment in synchronous and asynchronous learning. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Asynchronous learning activities, such as recorded lectures and discussion forums, offer students the opportunity to engage with course materials at their own pace, which is an indicator of adaptability and personalized learning in the blended environment (4.10), A balanced integration of synchronous and asynchronous elements is an indicator of a carefully designed blended learning environment that combines the benefits of structured live sessions with the flexibility of self-directed study (3.50), Synchronous learning, through

The results explain that asynchronous learning involves students engaging with pre-recorded lectures, discussion forums, or assignments independently. This approach grants learners greater flexibility in managing their schedules and allows them to access content when it suits them best. Synchronous and asynchronous elements signify a balanced integration that accommodates varying student schedules, time zones, and learning styles. These learning modes indicate the adaptability and inclusivity of a blended learning environment, allowing students to engage with course materials in ways that align with their individual preferences and needs while supporting the overarching educational objectives. Online learning and teaching became globally popular due to the impact of COVID-19. The pandemic has made both synchronous and asynchronous online learning inevitable in regions privileged with technological affordance. Zhang, Bi, and Mercado (2023) examine and compare the ef-

live virtual classes and discussions, provides students with real-time interaction opportunities, indicating an emphasis on immediate engagement and dynamic communication (3.45) and The availability of both synchronous and asynchronous learning activities within a blended learning environment is indicative of a flexible approach that accommodates varying student schedules and preferences (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Offering both synchronous and asynchronous options acknowledges the diverse needs of students, including those with different time zones, work commitments, or learning styles, making it an indicator of inclusivity in the blended learning approach (3.45) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.54 denotes the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of synchronous and asynchronous learning, which is oftentimes manifested and, thus, extensive.

fectiveness of both learning modes through the Community of Inquiry framework. The paired-sample t-test results indicated a significant difference in social presence, cognitive presence, and self-evaluated performance. Teaching presence significantly influenced social presence and cognitive presence in both learning modes. However, social presence significantly impacted self-evaluation, grades, and school identification under synchronous learning mode. Social presence only influenced school identification in an asynchronous learning mode. Theoretical and practical implications were also included.

3.1.4. Assessment Methods—Assessment methods are a critical indicator of a blended learning environment, reflecting the commitment to evaluating student progress and ensuring that learning objectives are met effectively. Assessment methods encompass various tools and techniques used to measure student understanding, knowledge acquisition, and skills development in a blended learning context. These

Table 3. The Extent of Blended Learning Environment in Terms of Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning

No	Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The availability of both synchronous and asynchronous learning activities within a blended learning environment is indicative of a flexible approach that accommodates varying student schedules and preferences.	3.40	Extensive
2	Synchronous learning, through live virtual classes and discussions, provides students with real-time interaction opportunities, indicating an emphasis on immediate engagement and dynamic communication.	3.45	Extensive
3	Asynchronous learning activities, such as recorded lectures and discussion forums, offer students the opportunity to engage with course materials at their own pace, which is an indicator of adaptability and personalized learning in the blended environment.	4.10	Extensive
4	A balanced integration of synchronous and asynchronous elements is an indicator of a carefully designed blended learning environment that combines the benefits of structured live sessions with the flexibility of self-directed study.	3.50	Extensive
5	Offering both synchronous and asynchronous options acknowledges the diverse needs of students, including those with different time zones, work commitments, or learning styles, making it an indicator of inclusivity in the blended learning approach.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.54	Extensive

methods include traditional exams, quizzes, essays, projects, and online assessments. The choice and design of these assessments align with the curriculum and are often informed by the blended learning environment’s digital resources and interactive components. Table 4 shows the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of the assessment method. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: The inclusion of both formative assessments (ongoing checks for understanding) and summative assessments (final evaluations) is an indicator of a holistic approach to monitoring and gauging student performance in the blended environment (4.10) is oftentimes manifested. The use of diverse assessment methods, such as traditional exams, essays, projects, and online quizzes, is an indicator of a comprehensive and balanced approach to evaluating student learning within the blended environment (3.30); the integration

of technology into the assessment process, such as online assessment platforms and e-portfolios, is an indicator of a technologically enhanced blended learning environment that leverages digital tools to support evaluation and feedback processes (3.25). The use of adaptive assessment tools that provide tailored feedback and adjust the difficulty of questions based on a student’s performance is an indicator of a personalized and learner-centered blended learning environment (3.10), and Assessments that closely align with course learning objectives demonstrate that the blended learning environment is designed with a clear focus on evaluating student progress and achievement in line with educational goals (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.35 denotes the extent of the blended learning environment in terms of the assessment method, which is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 4. The Extent of the Blended Learning Environment in Terms of Assessment Method

No	Assessment Method	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The use of diverse assessment methods, such as traditional exams, essays, projects, and online quizzes, is an indicator of a comprehensive and balanced approach to evaluating student learning within the blended environment.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Assessments that closely align with course learning objectives demonstrate that the blended learning environment is designed with a clear focus on evaluating student progress and achievement in line with educational goals.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
3	The inclusion of both formative assessments (ongoing checks for understanding) and summative assessments (final evaluations) is an indicator of a holistic approach to monitoring and gauging student performance in the blended environment.	4.10	Extensive
4	The use of adaptive assessment tools that provide tailored feedback and adjust the difficulty of questions based on a student's performance is an indicator of a personalized and learner-centered blended learning environment.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
5	The integration of technology into the assessment process, such as online assessment platforms and e-portfolios, is an indicator of a technologically enhanced blended learning environment that leverages digital tools to support evaluation and feedback processes.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.35	Moderately Extensive

Well-structured assessment methods signal an institution's emphasis on academic rigor and accountability in the blended learning model. It also signifies the ability to adapt assessment strategies to suit different learning modalities, in-person or online, and provides students with a comprehensive understanding of their progress. Moreover, effective assessment methods in blended learning environments support educators in making data-informed decisions, personalizing instruction, and ensuring that students achieve the desired learning outcomes while maintaining the integrity of the educational experience. As a result of scientific and technological developments reflection, improvements in education science moved from teacher-centered to student and learning-centered systems. Learning concepts are not only seen

in schools and some learning centers but also in all areas and places of life. Çiftçi (2020) searches for the achievement and persistence of blended learning methods in social studies lessons. As a dependent variable, the social studies academic success test results have been searched. For the determined dependent variables, an assessment between groups was applied according to pre-test and post-test scores. According to the findings, no difference has been found between pre-test scores. According to post-test and persistency test, a significant difference has appeared in favor of the experimental group, which is the blended learning method. According to repeated measures analyses, results between pre-test and post-test and between post-test and persistency test, as well as comparison of pre-test and post-test, both af-

fect student achievement. However, according to the results, the effect of blended learning is larger. According to the post-test and persistency score results, blended learning is more effective than face-to-face learning for knowledge persistence. According to the results of the persistency test and final application, which compares blended learning and face-to-face learning, a blended learning group is more effective than a face-to-face learning group. While the face-to-face learning group's final application score lessened by 12 points, the blended learning group's score decreased by 8 points. It can be confessed that, due to the persistence of student achievement, the blended learning method is more effective than the face-to-face learning method. Uygur (2022) investigated the effect of the blended learning method enriched by material development in elementary school social studies courses on students' academic achievement and explored their views towards this model. By the end, it was concluded that the experimental group, exposed to

blended learning activities enriched by material development, scored statistically significantly higher in academic achievement than the control group. The students found the method entertaining and educational. Table 5 shows the summary of the extent of the blended learning environment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: online content (4.24) is always manifested; synchronous and asynchronous learning (3.54) and learning management system (3.36) are oftentimes manifested, and assessment methods (3.35) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.00 denotes that the extent of the blended learning environment is oftentimes manifested and, thus, extensive. Blended learning, which combines the benefits of online and face-to-face instruction, is becoming popular in higher education. Despite its increasing application, more research is needed on the mechanisms to improve student performance in blended learning courses.

Table 5. Summary of the Extent of Blended Learning

No	Blended Learning	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Online Content	4.24	Very Extensive
2	Learning Management System	3.36	Extensive
3	Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning	3.54	Extensive
4	Assessment Methods	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		4.00	Extensive

Cannon et.al. (2023) identify and empirically test individual factors influencing student performance in an introductory marketing course offered in a blended learning format. Through two surveys conducted during the semester at two large public business schools, we find that metacognitive regulation,

metacognitive knowledge, and student effort enhance student performance in blended learning courses. Authors find that self-efficacy and course-specific attitudes affect metacognition and student effort. Based on the results, they provide practical strategies to design blended learning courses that improve stu-

dent performance. Kara et al. (2023) investigate the attitudes of elementary-level teachers toward blended learning implementation in Turkey. Quantitative data were gathered with a survey instrument that measures the perception of teachers on blended learning. The qualitative data was collected by conducting individual interviews with open-ended questions with ten participants. The results of quantitative data and qualitative findings indicated that teachers generally have a positive attitude toward implementing blended learning in elementary education (Kara et al., 2023).

3.2. Student Engagement—Student engagement refers to students' active involvement, participation, and investment in their own learning experiences. It encompasses a range of behaviors, attitudes, and strategies that indicate a student's commitment to and enthusiasm for learning. Engaged students are typically motivated, curious, and willing to try to master the subject matter. They actively participate in class discussions, ask questions, seek clarification, and demonstrate genuine interest in learning. Student engagement is not limited to academic activities; it also extends to a student's extracurricular activities, interactions with peers and teachers, and emotional connection to the educational environment. In essence, student engagement is a multifaceted concept that reflects the depth of a student's connection to their education, fostering better learning outcomes and personal growth.

3.2.1. Completion of Assignment—Completing assignments as a factor of student engagement refers to the extent to which students actively and responsibly fulfill their academic tasks and responsibilities. It reflects their commitment to the learning process and willingness to invest time and effort in completing assignments, projects, and assessments. When students consistently complete assignments on time and at a high level of quality, it indicates a strong engagement with the subject matter and

the educational objectives. This aspect of engagement also demonstrates a sense of personal responsibility and accountability in meeting academic requirements, contributing to a positive learning environment and fostering academic success. Students who regularly complete assignments are more likely to actively participate in their education, demonstrate their understanding of the material, and work toward achieving their learning goals. Table 6 shows the extent of student engagement in terms of completion of assignments. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: The consistent and timely submission of assignments demonstrates a high level of student engagement, indicating that students are actively participating in their coursework (4.00), Completing assignments that reflect a deep understanding of the subject matter is a strong indicator that students are actively engaged in learning and are mastering the material (3.54) and Students who consistently produce high-quality assignments are likely deeply engaged in the learning process, as they put in the effort to produce thoughtful and well-executed work (3.36) are oftentimes manifested. When students go beyond basic requirements and demonstrate creativity or innovative thinking in their assignments, they are motivated and engaged in exploring the subject matter (3.35). When students voluntarily take on additional assignments or extra credit work, it shows a high level of engagement and a desire to go above and beyond in their studies (3.16) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.48 denotes that the extent of student engagement in terms of completion of assignments is oftentimes manifested and, thus, extensive. Academic task completion is essential to school success, and academic activity across individuals appears to be maintained by different variables. Peters et al. (2022) assess variables that might promote higher or lower levels of academic engagement. All participants showed

the lowest rates of academic engagement in the distraction condition. The condition with the highest level of completion varied across par-

ticipants. The results of this study suggest that the context may be just as important for task completion as social reinforcement.

Table 6. The Extent of Student Engagement in Terms of Completion of Assignment

No	Completion of Assignment	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The consistent and timely submission of assignments demonstrates a high level of student engagement, indicating that students are actively participating in their coursework.	4.00	Extensive
2	Students who consistently produce high-quality assignments are likely deeply engaged in the learning process, as they put in the effort to produce thoughtful and well-executed work.	3.36	Extensive
3	Completing assignments that reflect a deep understanding of the subject matter is a strong indicator that students are actively engaged in learning and are mastering the material.	3.54	Extensive
4	When students go beyond basic requirements and demonstrate creativity or innovative thinking in their assignments, it suggests they are motivated and engaged in exploring the subject matter.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5	When students voluntarily take on additional assignments or extra credit work, it shows a high level of engagement and a desire to go above and beyond in their studies.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.48	Extensive

Soffer and Cohen (2019) examined students' engagement characteristics in online courses and their impact on academic achievements, trying to distinguish between course completers and no completers. The results revealed significant differences between students who completed the courses and students who did not in all 13 variables. Completers' learning activities were more than twice as high, except for writing in the forums. Course subject and ongoing task and assignment submissions predicted course completion, whereas, in addition to these variables, engagement with course materials and reading the forums predicted final exam success, as well.

3.2.2. *Quality of Work*—The quality of work as a factor of student engagement relates

to the depth, thoroughness, and excellence students approach their academic tasks and assignments. It signifies the extent to which students invest time and effort to produce work demonstrating a high level of understanding, critical thinking, and mastery of the subject matter. Engaged students consistently strive for excellence, aiming to produce work beyond basic requirements. Table 7 shows the extent of student engagement in terms of quality of work. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: When students incorporate original ideas, creative solutions, or innovative approaches into their work, it suggests a deep engagement with the material and a willingness to think beyond the surface level (3.54) is oftentimes manifested.

High-quality work often reflects a keen attention to detail, indicating that students are invested in producing accurate and precise assignments (3.20). Quality work is characterized by clear and effective communication of ideas. Students who can convey their thoughts concisely and coherently are actively engaged in the process of articulating their understanding (3.15). Students who consistently seek to revise and improve their work based on feedback demonstrate a commitment to learning and a desire to en-

hance the quality of their assignments, which is a strong indicator of engagement (3.10) and Students who produce work that demonstrates thorough research, critical thinking, and in-depth analysis show a high level of engagement in the subject matter (3.00) are sometimes manifested The overall mean rating of 3.48 denotes that extent of student engagement in terms of quality of work is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 7. The Extent of Student Engagement in Terms of Quality of Work

No	Quality of Work	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Students who produce work that demonstrates thorough research, critical thinking, and in-depth analysis show a high level of engagement in the subject matter.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	High-quality work often reflects a keen attention to detail, indicating that students are invested in producing accurate and precise assignments.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	When students incorporate original ideas, creative solutions, or innovative approaches into their work, it suggests a deep engagement with the material and a willingness to think beyond the surface level.	3.54	Extensive
4	Quality work is characterized by clear and effective communication of ideas. Students who can convey their thoughts concisely and coherently are actively engaged in the process of articulating their understanding.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	Students who consistently seek to revise and improve their work based on feedback demonstrate a commitment to learning and a desire to enhance the quality of their assignments, which is a strong indicator of engagement.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.19	Moderately Extensive

The quality of work reflects their commitment to the learning process, motivation to excel, and dedication to achieving academic success. This factor is not limited to the correctness of answers but extends to the clarity of communication, originality, and the demonstration of higher-order thinking skills. In essence, the quality of work is a key indicator of the depth of a student's engagement with the content and the educational process, ultimately leading to

a more meaningful and effective learning experience. Adesina et al. (2023) investigate the impact of peer assessment on students' engagement in their learning in a group work context. Findings suggest that students' perception of their contribution to group work fosters engagement and enhances their learning in a group. Also, students' perception and the overall experience of rating their peers' work impact their engagement within a group. The study con-

tributes to the literature by focusing on assessing the entire learning journey within a group rather than the final group output. Using an expectancy-value theory framework, Poort et al. (2023) investigate the extent to which the different components of this theory (i.e., self-efficacy, perceived benefit, and perceived cost) relate to each other and contribute to student engagement in IGW. In structural equation modeling analyses, self-efficacy and emotional cost emerge as significant predictors of behavioral and cognitive engagement; intercultural benefit is critical for cognitive engagement. As a prerequisite of cognitive engagement, behavioral engagement also mediates the effects of self-efficacy, costs, and benefits. Therefore, developing students' self-efficacy, increasing the perceived benefits of IGW, and decreasing the perceived costs of IGW can promote student engagement and deeper learning. Based on the results, authors theorize about the relationships among the components of the expectancy-value theory.

3.2.3. Inquiry and Curiosity—The concept of inquiry and curiosity as student engagement factors pertains to a student's natural inclination to explore, question, and seek a deeper understanding of the subject matter. It reflects their inquisitiveness, desire to learn, and active participation in the learning process. Engaged students often exhibit a sense of curiosity, asking questions, probing for more information, and showing an interest in exploring beyond the surface level of the curriculum. They are motivated by a genuine desire to discover, investigate, and connect knowledge, which leads to a more profound and meaningful learning experience. The presence of inquiry and curiosity as engagement factors indicates that students are not passive recipients of information but proactive and self-directed learners who seek to broaden their knowledge and develop critical thinking skills. These qualities contribute to a more dynamic and interactive educational environment, foster-

ing more tremendous academic success and a love for lifelong learning. Table 8 shows the extent of student engagement in terms of inquiry and curiosity. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: A willingness to explore topics beyond the core curriculum and delve into multidisciplinary subjects is an indicator of curiosity and engagement (3.45) and When students take the initiative to conduct independent research beyond the required curriculum, it reflects a strong desire to explore and learn, indicating a high level of engagement (3.40) are oftentimes manifested. Students who proactively ask questions and seek clarification on complex topics exhibit a high degree of curiosity and are actively engaged in the learning process (3.30), Students who actively engage in classroom discussions, share their insights, and offer alternative perspectives show a strong interest in the subject matter and are actively involved in the learning process (3.25) and Students who willingly take on challenging assignments, projects, or research opportunities demonstrate not only curiosity but also a readiness to tackle complex problems, which is a strong indicator of engagement in their academic pursuits (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.32 denotes that extent of student engagement in terms of inquiry and curiosity is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. According to policy documents and research studies, one key objective of science education is to develop students' inquiry abilities; however, more is needed to know about the interplay among students' inquiry abilities, the dimensions of their engagement, and their inquiry-related curiosity. Wu and Wu (2020) explore how four dimensions of engagement (i.e., cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social) were driven by inquiry-related curiosity and how they affected the students' inquiry abilities. The results showed that students' curiosity was associated with their inquiry abilities, and such an association was par-

tially mediated by the four dimensions of engagement in science laboratory classes. Moreover, the results revealed that among the four dimensions of engagement, only cognitive and emotional engagement had significant total effects on students' inquiry abilities and that the

influence of behavioral and social engagement on inquiry abilities was entirely mediated by cognitive engagement. This study suggests a critical role of emotional engagement, cognitive engagement, and curiosity in developing students' inquiry abilities.

Table 8. The Extent of Student Engagement in Terms of Inquiry and Curiosity

No	Inquiry and Curiosity	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Students who proactively ask questions and seek clarification on complex topics exhibit a high degree of curiosity and are actively engaged in the learning process.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	When students take the initiative to conduct independent research beyond the required curriculum, it reflects a strong desire to explore and learn, indicating a high level of engagement.	3.40	Extensive
3	A willingness to explore topics beyond the core curriculum and delve into multidisciplinary subjects is an indicator of curiosity and engagement.	3.45	Extensive
4	Students who actively engage in classroom discussions, share their insights, and offer alternative perspectives show a strong interest in the subject matter and are actively involved in the learning process.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
5	Students who willingly take on challenging assignments, projects, or research opportunities demonstrate not only curiosity but also a readiness to tackle complex problems, which is a strong indicator of engagement in their academic pursuits.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.32	Moderately Extensive

Wu et al. (2018) address the issue of curiosity-driven inquiry learning by examining the interplay among students' inquiry-related curiosity, laboratory engagement, and inquiry abilities and investigate how their learning experiences would associate with such interplay. The results revealed that, for students from both grades, inquiry-related curiosity was associated with their inquiry abilities and that their inquiry-related laboratory engagement mediated the association. Furthermore, the analyses showed that formal and informal experiences were associated with the laboratory engagement of students from both grades through curiosity. However, the results indicated that, although the

roles of the two types of experiences varied in the associations, formal science experience had stronger associations with students' inquiry abilities than informal science experience for both graders.

3.2.4. *Initiative in Research or Project—*

The concept of initiative in research projects as a factor of student engagement pertains to a student's proactive and self-directed approach to academic research and projects. It reflects their willingness to take ownership of their learning, seeking out opportunities to explore, investigate, and create new knowledge independently. Engaged students who exhibit initiative in research projects are motivated by a desire to go beyond

the standard curriculum, to delve deeper into subjects that interest them, and to contribute original insights to their field of study. They lead in identifying research topics, designing methodologies, and actively seeking resources and guidance when necessary. This proactive attitude enhances their academic growth and fosters a sense of empowerment and self-efficacy. Initiative in research projects is a strong indicator of a student’s engagement with their education, as it demonstrates a commitment to active learning, problem-solving, and the pursuit of intellectual challenges. Table 9 shows the extent of student engagement in terms of initiative in

research or projects. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Engagement is evident when students actively participate in original research, contribute new insights or findings to their field, and are willing to share their work with a broader audience, whether through presentations, publications, or exhibitions (4.20) is always manifested. Students who pursue in-depth research or projects related to their special interests and passions display a strong commitment to personal and academic growth, driven by their own curiosity (3.50) is oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. The Extent of Student Engagement in Terms of Initiative in Research or Project

No	Initiative in Research or Project	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Students who take the initiative to undertake independent research projects beyond the classroom curriculum demonstrate a high level of engagement and a genuine passion for learning.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
2	The development of self-initiated, innovative projects or initiatives, whether academic or extracurricular, showcases a proactive approach to learning and engagement.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
3	Students who take the lead in organizing and executing group projects or collaborative research efforts exhibit a high degree of engagement and the ability to inspire and motivate their peers.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
4	Students who pursue in-depth research or projects related to their special interests and passions display a strong commitment to personal and academic growth, driven by their own curiosity.	3.50	Extensive
5	Engagement is evident when students actively participate in original research, contribute new insights or findings to their field, and are willing to share their work with a broader audience, whether through presentations, publications, or exhibitions.	4.20	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		3.50	Extensive

Students who take the lead in organizing and executing group projects or collaborative research efforts exhibit a high degree of engagement and the ability to inspire and motivate their peers (3.35), The development of self-initiated,

innovative projects or initiatives, whether academic or extracurricular, showcases a proactive approach to learning and engagement (3.25) and Students who take the initiative to undertake independent research projects beyond the class-

room curriculum demonstrate a high level of engagement and a genuine passion for learning (3.20) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.50 denotes that the extent of student engagement in terms of initiative in research or projects is often manifested, thus extensive. Student engagement is regarded as a critical educational outcome. However, it has proven elusive to educators within technical domains, such as marketing research and analytics, which has inspired the exploration of experiential course design elements. Yuksel et.al. (2021) utilize a mixed-methods design to examine CSPs and their effectiveness in marketing research and analytics courses. In Study 1, qualitative research yields student insights regarding the desired characteristics of a CSP. Study 2 illustrates that CSPs boost student engagement through perceptions of course relevance. However, students' subjective interest in the client represented a boundary condition for this effect. That is, CSPs did not offer value to students who lacked inherent interest in the client. In Study 3, a discrete choice model analysis outlined what attributes make clients interesting for students. Finally, Study 4 utilizes a field experiment to identify project-framing tactics that increase student interest through enhanced client familiarity. A series of recommendations are provided to maximize the efficacy of CSPs to marketing research and analytics courses. Modeling, the process of constructing, testing, and refining models, is an important skill in experimental physics and, thus, a learning goal of many physics laboratory classes. One promising approach to help students develop modeling skills is incorporating multiweek student-designed projects into lab courses. To assess the potential benefits of these projects in enhancing students' modeling abilities, we analyzed projects from three

upper-division lab courses at different institutions. By looking at written student coursework and student interviews, we investigated which parts of the modeling process the students from each project undertook and how this engagement in modeling differed depending on the features of the projects. The projects in our dataset varied widely, showing evidence of how students engaged with model construction and revisions. Borish et al. (2022) observed that the features of the projects, such as the goal and complexity of the required apparatus, were associated with how the students constructed models and enacted revisions. This has implications for how instructors may frame and structure courses with student-designed lab projects. Table 10 shows the summary of the extent of student engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: initiative in research or project (3.50) and completion of assignment (3.48), which are often manifested. Inquiry and curiosity (3.32) and quality of work (3.19) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.00 denotes that the extent of student engagement is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. Research on student engagement has recently gained popularity as it can address problems such as early dropout and poor achievement. Yang, et.al., (2023) reviewed how student engagement studies were undertaken during ERT from three perspectives: (1) the landscape of studies, (2) methodologies issues, and (3) the strategies used to facilitate student engagement. 42 articles were analyzed from an initial pool of 436 search results. The findings illustrate that current studies were predominately undertaken in the United States (36 percent) and China (22 percent) focusing on STEM subjects as a dominant discipline.

The literature could have been more consistent in defining and measuring student engage-

ment. In addition, most studies (57 percent) investigated students' engagement from the per-

Table 10. Summary of the Extent of Student Engagement

No	Student Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Completion of Assignment	3.48	Extensive
2	Quality of Work	3.19	Moderately Extensive
3	Inquiry and Curiosity	3.32	Moderately Extensive
4	Initiative in Research or Project	3.50	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.00	Moderately Extensive

spective of students, unlike other stakeholders. The most prominent finding is that ERT promoted several essential engagement strategies, including motivational factors, teachers’ facilitation, a hybrid learning model, and using learning technologies to boost students’ engagement. Siregar et.al. (2023) examine the moderating role of feedback in the influence between lecturer leadership, lecturer engagement, and student engagement. The study results show that although feedback affects student engagement, feedback does not act as a moderator in the influence between lecturer leadership, lecturer engagement, and student engagement. Meanwhile, lecturer engagement was found not to affect student engagement, but lecturer engagement significantly affected student engagement. In learning, lecturers must pay attention to feed-

back and lecturer leadership if lecturers expect high student engagement. This implies that lecturers must provide feedback and practice lecturer leadership in the classroom.

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Blended Learning Environment and Student Engagement*—Table 11 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between the blended learning environment and student engagement. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that no significant relationship between blended learning environment and student engagement must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between blended learning environment ($r=0.887$; $p_i.000$) and student engagement.

Table 11. Significant Relationship between Blended Learning Environment and Student Engagement

Variables	Blended Learning Environment	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Student Engagement		0.887	0.000	Significant	Reject H0

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$.

The relationship between a blended learning environment and student engagement is significant, contributing to a dynamic and interactive educational experience. Blended learning, which combines traditional face-to-face instruc-

tion with online components, creates a flexible and personalized approach to learning (Piña, 2022). This flexibility allows students to access educational content at their own pace and convenience, fostering a sense of autonomy and self-

directed learning. Incorporating digital tools, multimedia resources, and interactive activities in the online component of blended learning captures students' attention and caters to diverse learning styles. Han et al. (2022) shared that this multimedia-rich environment enhances student engagement by making the learning experience more interactive, collaborative, and relevant to their daily lives. Additionally, Kara et al. (2023) investigated the flexibility of blended learning that accommodates a variety of learning preferences, enabling students to engage with content in ways that suit their individual needs. Through the combination of in-person and online elements, blended learning encourages active participation, critical thinking, and collaboration, cultivating a positive and immersive educational experience for students. Integrating technology and face-to-face interactions in a blended learning environment creates a harmonious synergy that captivates students' interests and fosters a deeper and more meaningful connection to the learning process.

3.4. *The Domains of Blended Learning Environments significantly Influence Student Engagement*—Table 12 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis of the domains of blended learning environments that significantly influence student engagement. Domains of blended learning environments significantly influence student engagement in terms of online content (0.000), learning management systems (0.001), synchronous and asynchronous (0.000), and assessment methods (0.001), suggesting that they are significantly influential in student engagement. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.855 suggests that 85.5 percent of blended learning environments explain student engagement. This provides empirical evidence that the domains of blended learning environments can account for and explain student engagement variability. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (253.877) and F-statistic are significant p_i.001, indicating that the model is significant in student engagement.

Table 12. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Blended Learning Environment Significantly Influencing Student Engagement

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.135	–	0.078	60.426	0.001	–
H (Intercept)	0.323	–	0.176	1.056	0.270	–
Online content	0.226	0.116	0.102	1.010	0.315	*Reject H
Learning Management System	0.242	0.115	0.135	1.299	0.186	*Reject H
Synchronous and Asynchronous	0.253	0.094	0.212	2.098	0.048	*Reject H
Assessment Method	0.213	0.085	0.211	2.098	0.088	*Reject H
R ²				0.855		
F-value				253.877		
p-value				<0.001		

Note. *Significant at p_i 0.05.

Cannon et al. (2023) identify the theory behind the blended learning environment's significant influence on student engagement. This theory

is grounded in educational models recognizing students' diverse learning preferences and needs. Blended learning combines traditional

face-to-face instruction with online elements, drawing from constructivism, social learning, and experiential learning theories. Constructivism emphasizes active learning, where students build their understanding through interaction with content and peers. Blended learning incorporates online components, enabling students to engage with multimedia resources, interactive simulations, and collaborative platforms that align with the constructivist approach. Social learning theories highlight the importance of collaboration and peer interaction in the learning process. By incorporating both in-person and online interactions, blended learning provides opportunities for students to collab-

orate virtually and in the physical classroom, fostering a social and supportive learning community (Kara et al., 2023). Ali et al. (2023) stated that experiential learning theory suggests hands-on experiences enhance learning outcomes. Blended learning often integrates practical, real-world applications through online simulations and face-to-face activities, promoting experiential learning. Overall, the theory behind blended learning aligns with these educational paradigms, emphasizing active, collaborative, and experiential learning. Thus, it significantly influences student engagement by catering to a spectrum of learning styles and preferences.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussions, and drawing of implications. Findings were based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions were based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the study's findings, which were given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The blended learning environment in terms of online content (4.24) was always manifested; synchronous and asynchronous learning (3.54) and learning management systems (3.36) are extensive, and assessment methods (3.35) are moderately extensive. The overall mean rating of 4.00 denotes that the extent of the blended learning environment was often manifested, thus extensive. The student engagement in terms of initiative in research or project (3.50) and completion of assignment (3.48) is extensive. Inquiry and curiosity (3.32) and quality of work (3.19) were moderately extensive. The overall mean rating of 3.00 denotes that the extent of student engagement was sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant relationship between the blended learning environment ($r=0.887$; $p_i.000$)

and student engagement. Domains of blended learning environments significantly influence student engagement in terms of online content (0.000), learning management system (0.001), synchronous and asynchronous (0.000), and assessment method (0.001), suggesting a significant influence on student engagement with an R2 value of 0.885 or 88.5

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions to wit; The blended learning environment in online content was always manifested; synchronous and asynchronous learning and learning management systems were extensive, and assessment methods were moderately extensive. The student engagement in terms of initiative in research or projects and completion of assignments were oftentimes manifested. Inquiry, curiosity, and quality of work were extensive; thus, they were moderately extensive. There was a significant relationship between a

blended learning environment and student engagement. Domains of blended learning environments significantly influenced student engagement in terms of online content, learning management systems, synchronous and asynchronous, and assessment methods, which significantly influence student engagement.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May encourage and facilitate ongoing professional development opportunities for educators within the district to enhance their skills in integrating technology effectively into teaching practices. This would ensure that teachers stay abreast of the latest instructional strategies related to blended learning and can provide optimal support to their students. Collaborate with relevant stakeholders to assess and improve the technological infrastructure in schools. Ensure schools can access reliable internet, updated hardware, and necessary software to support a seamless blended learning environment. Establish a system for continuous monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of blended learning. Regularly assess the impact on student engagement, academic performance, and teacher effectiveness. Use the feedback to make informed decisions and adjust the blended learning initiatives. School Principal. May Organize regular training sessions and workshops for teachers to enhance their proficiency in utilizing blended learning tools and techniques. This would empower teachers to create engaging and effective blended learning experiences for their students. Develop and implement a comprehensive technology integration plan for the school.

This plan should outline how technology would support teaching and learning goals and how it aligns with the school's overall educational objectives. Foster communication with parents to keep them informed about the benefits and challenges of blended learning. Encourage parental involvement in supporting students' technological needs at home and provide resources to help parents understand the blended learning approach. Teachers. May tailor instructional strategies to meet the diverse needs of students, considering their learning styles and preferences. Provide additional support or resources for students who may face challenges adapting to the blended learning environment. Encourage collaboration among teachers to share best practices, resources, and lesson plans related to blended learning. This collaborative approach could foster a supportive teaching community within the school. Engage in regular self-reflection on the effectiveness of blended learning strategies employed in the classroom. Seek feedback from students and colleagues to identify areas for improvement and refinement. Future Researchers. May Undertake comparative analyses of different blended learning models and implementations to identify best practices. Explore how variations in technology use, teacher training, and student demographics may influence outcomes. Incorporate qualitative research methods, such as interviews and focus groups, to gain deeper insights into the subjective experiences of students, teachers, and parents in the blended learning environment. Understanding their perspectives could inform future improvements and innovations in blended learning initiatives.

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